

Non-Trajectory Intervals in Lorentz Invariants and Quantum Mechanics Part 2

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Quantum mechanics for a free particle involves uncertainties in x and t even though a trajectory is still certain ($x=vt$) and follows Newtonian mechanics as are E and p . In other words, there is probability in quantum mechanics, but not in Newtonian mechanics and this begs the question: Why? In Newtonian mechanics, if one has two m_0 rest masses and applies different forces to them such that one reaches a speed of v_1 and the other v_2 , then the two are clearly different, i.e. have different energies and momenta. The momenta may be measured by the impact of a strike against a target. There is no uncertainty in time or space in such a scenario which again leads to the question: How can there be uncertainty in quantum mechanics?

We have argued in Part I that this uncertainty in x,t follows from the enforcement of a Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ by using intervals dt and dx which have nothing to do with a trajectory ($x=vt$). The point we wish to make here is that in special relativity, it is not only ($p=0, m_{\text{occ}}$) which transforms under a Lorentz transformation but ($x=0, ct$) as well. In other words, work on a particle not only changes its E and p (in Newtonian mechanics), but also its spacetime and this must be physically manifest in a measurable way which affects interactions, we argue. Thus, mapping (x,ct) to (x',ct') as trajectory points does not demonstrate such a property.

For p , a change is manifest by a stronger impulse, but we argue that spacetime changes can only be manifest through interval changes. This necessarily involves uncertainty in x,t and information. In other words, the uncertainty in dx and dt follows from the certainty of $dA=0 = -Edt + p dx$ in any frame (for constant v). It appears as a way to offset the change in E and p so as to make $dA=0$. Thus, Newtonian thinking must be changed to include two sets of changes when a particle is accelerated to a constant v , namely a change in (p,E) and a change in dx,dt . The interesting feature is that the spacetime change involves probability and information. Increasing p means a stronger impulse, but also a sharper $dx = \hbar/p$ meaning that one may discern two slits separated by \hbar/p , something that cannot be done for a much lower p . Thus, there is an information gain and the idea of entropy is present. Overall, however, $dA=0$ and so a gain of information in dx goes hand-in-hand with a strong impulse hit and work done on the particle.

Newtonian Acceleration of a Particle

If one considers two m_0 rest masses and accelerates one to v_1 and the other to v_2 (constant speeds), then the two have different energies and masses and represent different states. If $v_1 < v_2$, then $p_1 < p_2$ and p_1 makes less of an impulse on a target. Spacetime is considered to be the same for both and there is no notion of any probability or entropy.

If one, however, considers the following scheme, then probability may be introduced. Momentum involves motion in space and so imagine that one wishes to discern the momenta p_1 and p_2 over the same length of space L . In such a case, one might consider measuring momentum in equal pieces so that: $p_1 = n_1 p$ and $p_2 = n_2 p$. Then for p_1 one requires $L/n_1 dx$ intervals, while for p_2 , L/n_2 intervals. In other words, there is a spacing difference or resolution

for the two. This involves information, however, because the smaller spacing represents more information about space. It is based, however, on the requirement that the same overall length be used to discern each p . In other words, there is something common to both p_1 and p_2 , namely L . This may seem like an artificial example, but special relativity introduces similar considerations which lead to the emergence of probability from certainty.

Special Relativistic Considerations

A fundamental difference between Newtonian mechanics and special relativity is that $(p=0, m_0 c)$ does not simply transform to (p, E) , but so does space time, i.e. $(x=0, ct) \rightarrow (x', ct')$. Not only that, but the same Lorentz matrix transforms both leading to a Lorentz invariant involving x', t', E, p as pointed out in Part I, i.e.

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((1))$$

We argued that for a given rest mass at rest in one frame, different frames with $-v_1, -v_2$ etc lead to sets of $(p_1, E_1), (p_2, E_2)$ etc, but each of these has the same invariant (1) and represents the same physical particle (m_0 at rest). Of course, if one had n particles at rest with m_0 and accelerated these to v_1, v_2, v_3 etc, then would argue, as in Newtonian physics, that they were completely different states with no Lorentz invariant linking them. Special relativity, however, introduces a common feature to each (p_i, E_i) , namely $A = -Et + px$. This means that to ensure this, if E and p change, one may introduce non-trajectory related intervals $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$ as argued in Part 1 to keep $dA = 0$. The reason for introducing non-trajectory dx and dt values is that E and p have physical consequences on an interaction and one wishes dx and dt to also have physical consequences (on an interaction). A mapping from x, ct to x', ct' does not achieve this.

This means, however, that in order to maintain certitude, $dA = 0$, one must introduce probability (through dx, dt) because that seems to be the only way for t and x to manifest changes physically. P (momentum) can manifest a physical change by delivering a stronger impulse hit to a target.

In other words, accelerating a particle not only changes E and p , but also dx and dt intervals if special relativity is to hold. This is necessary for $dA = 0 = -E dt + p dx$ to exist even if one accelerates several m_0 masses at rest in the same frame. In other words, there is a direct connection between E, p and x, t and so changes to one set imply changes to the other. The latter can only involve probability and this is linked to information. These dx and dt intervals are linked to interactions as the classical Newtonian trajectory $x = vt$ still holds, as argued in Part I.

Information

As a result, accelerating a particle gives it a p which makes deliver stronger impulse hits, but because x is involved and must offset a change in p , it has a dx linked with resolution information in space. In other words, a high p means a high dx which can resolve two slits separated by \hbar/p and interact with both leading to an entangled state. As a result, acceleration does not simply change E, p (making p yield strong impulses) and $x = vt$ as in

Newtonian mechanics, but it introduces dx and dt intervals which introduce information and probability because special relativity shows that not only p, E transform, but also x, ct . Thus, work accelerating a particle gives it more spatial information and if E increases, more temporal resolution in interactions.

This is a different viewpoint from considering infinite t and x resolution in any frame and simply viewing a Lorentz transformation on (x, ct) as mapping one point to another (x', ct') . It suggests that a physical change occurs when $(p=0, m_0 c)$ maps to (p, E) and that a physical change must also occur to x, t , which implies interval changes and probability. This, we argue, is the reason for the emergence of probability in free particle quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that in Newtonian mechanics accelerating two rest masses m_0 , to v_1 and v_2 (constant speeds) changes E and p in a physical manner which may be measured, i.e. through collisions with a target. There is no notion of a change to spacetime or probability.

Special relativity, however, uses the same Lorentz transformation to change $(p=0, m_0 c)$ to (p, E) which is manifested physically through target collisions, but also changes x, ct to x', ct' . At first, this may seem as a mapping of x', ct' so that $(x=0, t=0) \rightarrow (x'=0, t'=0)$ yields a new x', t' such that $x'=vt'$ as seen in the moving frame, but we argue that there should be a physical interaction changing x, t and this seems to be manifested through intervals $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$. p, E change with physical consequences (which represent a state change) related to interactions and x', t' should change in a similar manner. dx and dt probability/resolution regions are introduced which are linked to interactions. The new p, E affect an interaction as do $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$. This puts the two 4-vectors (p, E) and (x, ct) on the same physical footing. The Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ (or $dA = -E dt + p dx$) connects the various (p, E) states, an idea that does not exist in Newtonian mechanics. As a result, changes to p, E and corresponding changes to dx, dt (not related to trajectories) such that $dA = 0$ result in probability/resolution/information being introduced in t and x and to free particle quantum mechanics.